

Role of Archaeological Survey of India For Conservation of Monuments of Ekamra Kshetra In Post-Independence Period

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Abstract

The city of temples was named after Tribhubaneswar, “Lord of three worlds” and its proud sculptural and architectural heritage, coupled with its sanctity as Ekamra Kshetra. The city apart from its spiritual, religious and architectural wealth, has abundance of archaeological evidence like ruins of Sisupalgarh (4th C.B.C.) is one of the best preserved early historic fortification in India, Ashokan rock edicts etc. Anyone concerned with historic monuments should have an awareness of the causes of decay. In addition to gravity, which is an ever-present cause of decay, climatic causes, biological causes, botanical causes, natural disasters such as flood and earth-quakes are also factors responsible for decay in monuments and sites. This paper attempts to highlight the major problems for protection, conservation and management aspects of some of the important monuments and sites of Ekamra Kshetra, Bhubaneswar.

Key Words- Ekamra Kshetra, Conservation, ASI

Bhubaneswar (Lat. 20° 15' N.; Long. 85° 50' E.) a sacred city with a cluster of magnificent well-preserved temples and many tanks, is the main centre of Odisha architecture. The city of temples was named after Tribhubaneswar, “Lord of three worlds” and its proud sculptural and architectural heritage, coupled with its sanctity as Ekamra Kshetra. Legends trace the sanctity of

the place, when there was a single mango tree with Sivalinga below it due to which the place is revered as Ekamra Khetra. The religious centre initially developed around it and with the construction of famous Lingraja temple in the 11th century, the Ekamra Kshetra was treated as major religious centre of Saivism. Mythological references and the epigraphic sources describe the area as Ekamra Kshetra and saiva pitha , one of the five great religious centres in Odisha since early medieval days , attracting thousands of visitors from all corners of the world throughout the year.

The Ekamra Kshetra or Ekamra Kanana was much more extensive than the present temple town. According to the orthodox texts, such as Svarnadari Mahodaya¹ and Ekamra Chandrika², it is extended from Khandacala (Khandagiri) on the west to Kundalesvara on the east; from Valahadevi on the north to Bahirangesvara at the top of the Dhauligiri in the south. The area is believed to be circular³ in shape, with Lingaraj temple as its centre. Another concept associated with the Kshetra is its division into eight ayatannas⁴, each with its water body, temples, small shrines, tirthas and prescribed/ ritual procession routes that are ritualistically and symbolically connected to the Lingaraj Temple.

In the narration of the eight ayatanas, the Ekamra Chandrika has been followed as it is later than Svarnadari Mahodaya.

The first ayatana Ekamra Ksetra includes Bindusara, Ananta Vasudeva, Devipadahara, Tirthesvara and Tribhubaneswar.

The second ayatana contains Maitresvara, Varunesvara, Isanesvara, Yamesvara and tirthas, such as Papanasana Kunda.

The third ayatana includes Ganga-Yamuna tirtha and the Sivalinga called Gangesvara.

The fourth ayatana contains several Sivalings, such as Kotisvara, Svarnajalesvara, Suparnajalesvara, Suresvara, Sidshesvara, Muktesvara, Kedaresvara, Rudralinga, Marutesvara, Daityesvara and Indresvara. The tirthas associated with the Sivalingas are Kotitirtha, Siddhakunda and Gaurikunda.

The fifth aytana contains the shrines of Brahmesvara, Gokarnesvara, Utpaiesvara, Amrtakesvara, Madhyamesvara and Jatilesvara, besides the Brahma Kunda.

The sixth aytana contains Lingas, such as Meghesvara, along with Meghakunda, Bhaskaresvara and its associated kundas and Kapalmocana Siva.

The seventh ayatana has Sivalingas, such as Alabukesvara with Alabu tirtha, Uttaresvara and Bhimesvara.

The eighth ayatana of the Ekamra Ksetra contains Ramesvara along with Rama Kunda, Sitesvara, Hanumadisvara, Lavanisvara, Bharatesvara, Laksmanesvara, Satrugnesvara, Gosahasresvara and Paradaresvara.

The old town structure was a not-geometric but organic derivative of the Mandala⁵ concept. The tanks such as Bindusagar, Devipadahara, Papanasini, Ganga-Yamuna, Kotitirthesvara, Brahma Kunda, Meghathirtha and Rama Kunda were attached with religious symbolisms and considered holy.

The city apart from its spiritual, religious and architectural wealth, has abundance of archaeological evidence like ruins of Sisupalgarh (4th C.B.C.) (ASI, 1949) is one of the best preserved early historic fortification in India, Ashokan rock edicts etc. Then remains of rock-cut caves at Udayagiri and Khandagiri, situated about 6 miles away to the north-west of the temple town. These caves with their bas-reliefs and Brahmi inscriptions seen in Hati Gumpha (Barua, 1929) throw considerable light on the early history of Kalinga and India in the 1st C. B.C. to 1st C. A.D.

The good condition of the temples, ranging over a period of nearly six centuries (between 7th to 13th C. A.D.) makes it fairly easy to investigate the evolution of the architectural type of the temples. Further, an inscription of 1235 A.D. found in the Mukhamanadap of the Amritesvara temple (Dept. of Archaeology, GOI., 1914-15) at Holal in Bellary district of Karanataka Speaks of a 4th style i.e. Kalinga in addition to the Nagara, Dravida and Vessara which exist in India. Two other valuable resources facilitate the study of this architectural mode, namely i) some ancient texts of the Orissan cannons of architecture, containing names and measurements of different parts

of the temple and ii) the oral traditions which are still kept alive among some living families of shapatis, descendants of the ancient *silpis* who built these places of worship.

Keeping this as backdrop, a humble attempt has been made here to highlight the major problems for protection, conservation and management aspects of some of the important monuments and sites of Ekamra Kshetra, Bhubaneswar.

Anyone concerned with historic monuments should have an awareness of the causes of decay. In addition to gravity, which is an ever-present cause of decay, climatic causes, biological causes, botanical causes, natural disasters such as flood and earth-quakes are also factors responsible for decay in monuments and sites. Moreover, decay is also caused due to vandalism of men. Apart from the structural and chemical preservation problems, the most serious danger caused to the monuments and sites is the rise of population and the consequent demand of more agricultural Land. In agricultural extension programme people grab land for cultivation within the archaeological area e.g. at Sisupalgarh and Churangarh by ignoring existence of priceless heritage. Government's consistent steps for raising the standard of rural life by various forms of economic development for more food are probably the primary causes of loss of the cultural heritage not only in Bhubaneswar area but also throughout Odisha.

Second major source of destruction of the cultural heritage comes from the quarrying of stone, the robbing of stone or other building material and digging of earth for variety of purposes. Recently due to quarrying of stone and murrum for widening of roads of National Highway No. 5 under Prime Minister Sadak Yojana, the protected area of Khandagiri-Udayagiri hills has been disturbed. A part of Udayagiri hill has been used as National high way No.5. At Sisupalgarh, Churangarh in khurdha district stone and brick members of the edifices have been frequently robbed off reusing the same in the palaces of local zamindars and houses of villagers etc. The robbing off of stones is a common phenomenon and has led to the destruction of fortification wall of Churangarh.

Thirdly, due to the urban development and consequent intrusion into historical sites many monuments and historical sites have been encroached by government and private bodies. Due to encroachment and construction around the Vaital Temple complex, the original outlet of complex

is blocked. As a result, during rainy season rain water could not drain out properly. And there is no approach road to reach the Paramaguru Temple, a centrally protected monument, close to this complex due to the illegal construction. Furthermore, archaeological sites are neglected or surrounded by poorly-planned commercial development. Thus, the fine architectural elements are gradually losing their importance.

Fourthly, due to laying out of roads and sewerage lines archaeological remains at Sisupalgarh have been badly disturbed. In many areas, there are encroachments and heritage routes have become narrower. This creates problems for the visiting tourists. Efforts should be made for conservation of built heritage and delineation of special zones for tourism promotion and development. Many temples at Ekamra Kshetra area are also badly affected due to this type of cause.

Fifthly, installation of telecommunication and electricity system in urban area and other activities by the government agencies badly affect the archaeological sites and monuments. Thus, the entire skyline is disturbed due to this type of activities along with unsystematic display of hoardings in the city close to the monuments and sites.

Sixthly, the uncontrolled growth of tourism both domestic and foreign poses a potential threat to the cultural heritage. Many motorable metalled roads have been built right up to the site, for example at Dhauli rock-edict site. A cluster of craft shops, small hotels and vendors' structures have cropped-up in the vicinity of Ekamra Kshetra area. As a result aesthetic environment of the monuments have been badly affected. These developments need to be carefully monitored and controlled. Khandagiri & Udayagiri complex in Bhubaneswar is another example of threat from developments due to tourism.

Tourism, if badly managed is a threat to historic monuments and antiquities. Crowds can damage the floors and walls of building. Sometimes sensible persons put graffiti mark and disfigure the ancient monuments and sites. This act is nothing but an act of heartless vandalism. Tourist can spread litter and refuses and spoil the pristine atmosphere of site. The uncontrolled growth of tourism in living monuments like Lingaraj temple and Jaina monuments at Khandagiri & Udayagiri near Bhubaneswar has caused heavy damage to the monuments through disfiguring

the walls and floor surfaces, light and sound show by I.T.D.C. and also through writing graffiti, putting the names and using paints, vermilion, oil, etc in doing so.

Another threat which arises as a concomitant of tourism and of growing international interest in the cultural heritage is in the form of pilfering the priceless artifacts and selling it in the world art markets. There are many examples of thefts and destruction of sculptures from unprotected, ruined temples in Bhubaneswar area or of illicit excavation in search of treasure or works of art.

To add to it, the management of the monuments and heritage sites in urban area are also facing multifarious problems. Lingaraj temple at Bhubaneswar is the best example in this regard. The shopkeepers around the premises of the temple, existing electricity wiring, poles, drains, buildings constructed for shops, offices, lodging and other structures for public utility have already acquired the outer periphery of the temple complex. This has created an unwanted congestion of old town area. Other monuments are also threatened by the land grabbing. A striking example of this is the Sisupalgarh, Paramaguru and Lingaraj temple Bhubaneswar, which have been emasculated by the construction of both residential as well as shopping complex in its' vicinity. Same is the situation around the Vaital, Ramesvara, Rajrani, Bhrahmesvara, Bhaskaresvara, Khandagiri & Udayagiri etc. It appears that man and his activities pose greater threats to the cultural heritage than nature. The threat posed by population pressure on the cultural heritage however can be marginally eased out but it will continue to pose threats to our heritage.

URBAN CONSERVATION:

During the last two decades, conservation has emerged as a powerful force in environmental programmes in India. The process of preservation and conservation of monuments and complexes including landscape in the aforesaid conservation programmes have been intensely incorporated. The two main aspects of the "conservation planning" are concerning with i) the wide problems of ecology, pollution, environmental degradation and ii) the other one specially dealing with the built environment. The countries like U.K. and France have already adopted conservation and environmental control programmes in respect of the buildings of historic and architectural

interest and the ancient sites of scenic beauty. Landscaping as an integral part of physical planning and development of the monuments and sites has also been successfully incorporated.

In spite of involvement of the central and state agencies and organizations for the preservation of cultural heritage, many shortcomings are also noticed in the maintenance of monuments in Ekamra Kshetra area (Dikshit, 2007: 44-45). Those are:-

1. Inadequacy of attendants and guides posted at most of the monuments and sites leading to improper maintenance and thefts;
2. Improper preservation of structures including a number of un-protected monuments in need of considerable repairs;
3. Poor maintenance of gardens and pathways concerning the monuments;
4. Lack of proper infrastructural facilities at and around the monuments like poor approach roads, inadequate bus services, inconvenient location of offices, inadequate lighting, poor food and drinking water facilities, lack of toilet facilities etc. discourage tourists from visiting the sites;
5. Mis-use of several monuments and sites;
6. Absence of identity boards, descriptions of the monument, signage as also non-availability of informative literature about the monuments;
7. Poor development of the surrounding region;
8. Problems of co-ordination between the Municipal body and the Department of Archaeology where the monuments are surrounded by parks and open spaces which are under the control of the Municipal Council; and
9. Inadequate provision in the Ancient Monuments Act for controlled development in the vicinity of protected monuments.

State Government is directly responsible for urban local administration and their policies and programmes have a far-reaching effect on the protection of monuments and their conservation. It must be admitted that, barring a few exceptions no serious effort in the cause of conservation has been taken by the State Government. Apart from these, there is lack of adequate provisions in

the Town Planning and Local legislation for effective conservation in line with those of the advanced countries. The efforts under taken by different agencies have fallen short of a comprehensive look at all the problems of total urban planning and conservation. There is no statute at the centre or state level for listing the sites and monuments of historic and architectural significance which will enable the state to take over historically important private buildings in t case of negligence.

HISTORY OF CONSERVATION:

With the ravages of time many of the monuments have either been partially damaged or needed immediate repairs. There are a number of evidences of repair and conservation of damaged monuments in contemporary literary texts such as, cannons, Puranas, historical records of medieval and British period. There are also a number of inscriptional evidences of ancient and medieval periods which reveal the steps taken by ancient and medieval rulers for repairs of damaged monuments, conferring grants for the maintenance and upkeep of monuments etc.

In the past, efforts have been made by successive rulers, societies and individuals for proper protection and preservation of monuments handed over by our predecessors'. It is for this repair works most of the relics of bygone times are still in sound condition, otherwise many of them would have been irretrievably lost. In our literature, the terms *khanda-sphutita* – *jirnoddhara* means repairing and renovation of monuments, *sphutita* for removal of soot occurred due to application of oil, growth of moss and lichen and *khanda-sphutita navakarma* means repairing and removing the portions which are mutilated and which have developed accretions. For new colour -washing or lime-washing the term used was *nav-suddha karma* and for vegetation removal the term *tarugulmanirmalikaarana* was used (Batra, 1996).

Jirnoddhara has been described in the religious texts as a religious merit. Repair, restoration and renovation of old and dilapidated shrines have been described as more meritorious than the establishment of new shrines. Buddhism attached great importance to *jirnoddhara*. As a result, many rulers, landlords, individuals and societies under took repair and renovation works.

LITERARY EVIDENCES :

There are also references of *jirnoddhara* (restorations) in the *Aparajita Prachcha* (Bhowmik, 2004) and in *Danakanda* of *Dharmasastra* (Bhowmik, 2004). The subject of *jirnoddhara* (rehabilitating old or dilapidated temples) is given at length in *Nirnaya Sindhu* (Bhowmik, 2004), the *Dharma Sindhu* the *Agni Purana* and other works which indicate that the practice of *jirnoddhara* must have been as old as the practice of temple construction.

INSCRIPTIONAL EVIDENCES :

There are a number of evidences of repair and renovation works of old monuments in inscription of ancient and medieval Orissa. The earliest reference comes from the Hatigumpha inscription of Kharavela (Sircar, 1991) of the *Chedi* dynasty . It is mentioned that in the very first year of his reign, Kharavel ordered for the repair of the gates, walls and structures that had been destroyed by cyclonic wind and constructed embankment, tanks and restored the damaged gardens. This cost him an amount of 35, 00,000 coins. This is one of the earliest recorded instance of repairs and maintenance of ancient buildings.

The Dhauli cave inscription of Santikara Deva (Banerji, 1923) of the Bhauma-Kara dynasty refers to the construction and repair of a Buddhist monastery. From the Lalatendu cave inscription of Udyota-kesari (Barnett,1982) we know about the repairs of the decayed tank and temples and about the setting up of the images of 24 *Tirthankaras* by the king.

The Lingaraj temple Inscription of Anangabhimadeva – III (Sircar, 1975) (Anka Year 34) throws interesting light on the provisions made for the periodical repairs to a *mandapa* of the temple. Five *vatikas* of land were given to a potter for repairing the roof of the *mandapa* once every twelve years. Two *vatikas* of land were given to a lime-maker (*churnakara*) for whitewashing the walls of the *mandapa* once a year and one *vatikas* of land was given to a sweeper (*jhadudara*) for sweeping the *mandapa* premises three times a day. It also records that repairs were carried out to the *natamandir* of the Lingaraj temple by Govinda, the Senapati of the monarch. It is also learnt that the *mandapa* was used for various auspicious celebrations connected with the deity (*parvotsava*).

CONSERVATION DURING THE BRITISH RULE IN ORISSA:

With the conquest of Orissa by the Britishers in 1803, a new phase in our history and culture started. Though they came as traders, they took interest in administration as well as in our culture. In earlier part of the rule they did not interfere with our education system, social customs and cultural wealth. But gradually when they came to know about our rich cultural heritage, they took interest not only in translating our ancient Sanskrit text into English but also in protecting and preserving our old dilapidated historical monuments. Had they not tried, many significant glories of our past would not have come to light. With the Britishers, the scientific conservation of our monuments was started.

GROUP OF THE TEMPLES AT BHUBANESWAR :

Towards the conservation of a group of the temples at Bhubaneswar in Orissa out of the estimated cost of Rs.3,777 a sum of Rs.380 was only spent during year 1922 - 1923. The temples affected comprised of the following : (a) The Lingaraja and subsidiary shrines, (b) Brahmesvara (c) Muktesvara, (d) Rajarani, (e) Parasuramesvara (f) Bhaskaresvara (g) Meghesvara, (h) Chitrakarini (i) Maitresvara (j) Vaital Deul, (k) Yamesvara, (l) Ananta Vasudev (m) Somesvara, (n) Sari Deul and (o) Siddhesvara. The work consists principally of fitting iron frames to the openings of each shrine infilled with expanded metal to exclude birds and animals from entering the interior. In certain cases similar gates were provided to the courtyard and entrance also. The eradication of jungle growth and harmful vegetation from these structures were undertaken, while in the case of the Chitrakarini temple a missing stone was replaced in the spire. Petty repair works were also done to the masonry in the temples of Mukteswara and Yameswara and a leaking roof was mended in the Maitresvara. Enclosures about the shrines were levelled and the earth was dressed tidily. These works were undertaken to complete the repairs commenced some year ago on the notification of the monuments as protected under the Ancient Monuments Preservation Act, VII of 1904. Objection was, however, raised to this procedure by the Hindu custodians of the shrines and as no satisfactory settlement could be reached, the notification of protection was withdrawn and the repairs then started were abandoned. As a special case, the Government of India had agreed

later on for the completion of these works at a cost of Rs.2,410 and for correction of certain faulty repairs carried out on several temples by the then Bengal Government between the year 1898 and 1902. Of all the temples enumerated above only the Rajarani shrine had been notified under the Ancient Monuments Preservation Act (vide Government notification No. 2488-E, dated the 1st November 1913) (ASI, 2003).

For repair of a number of temples at Bhubaneswar, which was in progress since 1922-23, a further sum of Rs.1,589 was spent during the year under review, making a total expenditure of Rs.3,000 against an estimated cost of Rs.4040. The works were of minor nature and covered fifteen different shrines (ASI, 2002: AR1924-25).

In 1925-26 certain repairs works on ten of the temples at Bhubaneswar which had started three years ago were brought to completion by the Archaeological Department as a special case, since the temples except the Rajarani, were not “Protected” monuments. A sum of Rs.491, against a late allotment of Rs.600, was spent on these repairs, which included the resetting of displaced stones in the Ramesvara temple, the underpinning of a ruined small subsidiary shrine in the Ananta Vasudev temple complex, treating the decayed stones of the Maitresvara and Chitrakarini temples with paraffin wax and the replacement by plain uncarved stones of the same buff colour as the original work of a modern restoration in white stone done some 26 years ago in the Rajarani temple. This modern restoration included an elaborately carved piece of the door architrave and the effect of the white patch against the old buff masonry served as a proof against any softening influence of the weather (ASI, 2002: AR1926-27).

CONSERVATION UNDER ARCHAEOLOGICAL SURVEY OF INDIA:

In order to take proper care of the monuments the British Government in the year 1861, established the Archaeological Survey of India and placed it under prominent archaeologists and historians. The Archaeological Survey of India, inspite of having many obstacles, did wonderful job in the field of conservation and restoration of our monuments which are very important treasures of our cultural heritage. Below is given a brief history of the conservation steps taken by the A.S.I.

ETHICS, PRINCIPLES AND AIM OF CONSERVATION:

Archaeological sites are irreplaceable cultural resources. The aim of architectural conservation (Feilden, 1989 : 3-4) is to prolong the life of heritage buildings and to build proper environment about the historic site, so that future generations can enjoy them also profitably as we are enjoying now. Conservation is the action to reduce further decay of the edifices. During the time of conservation it is to be ensured that historic evidences shall not be destroyed, falsified or removed. Any intervention must be governed by ensuring respect for the aesthetic, historical and physical integrity of the cultural property. Our aim is to preserve the monument without alteration since it is the authentic part of the old structures and our interest is attached to it. The broken or half decayed original work is infinitely more valuable than the smartest and most perfect new work (Feilden, 1989 : 4-5).

Our aim should be (a) that every original member of a building should be preserved intact, demolition and reconstruction should be undertaken only if the structure could not be maintained otherwise, (b) restoration of carved stones, carved wood or plaster, moldings should be undertaken only if artisans are able to retain the excellence of old characteristics, (c) in no case any mythological or other scenes should be recarved (Marshall, 1973).

The following are the guide lines for carrying out repairs to certain important items of work:

1. While carrying out plaster work, the original mortar should be used and the contiguous objects must be matched in colour and texture.
2. Similarly, while replacing the veneering stones, the colour should match with the adjacent areas and the stones should be procured from the original quarry. Sculpture work need not be restored. Only carving or geometrical pattern may be restored if necessary to harmonize with the original. The new work is to be distinguished from the old work. However, while replacing the rubble stone masonry or ashlar stone masonry, care should be taken that the courses as per original character be maintained.
3. Same is the case with pavement, brick masonry etc. The modern bricks are not required to be used in the old work. While repairing any old buildings, efforts be made to procure old

bricks. Bricks of the same size and the fabric as the original must be used as the bricks to be laid on the same bond and the mortar joints should be of the same thickness and same tone of colour as in the old work where these are desired.

During the time of final conservation estimates are prepared on the basis of the conservation notes. As per prescribed rules the estimates must be supported by photographs of monuments before conservation along with the site plan, contour plan showing the conservation items and the technical reports in detail. To begin with the work of conservation one has to root out all destructive vegetation which are otherwise serious damaging agency to the monuments. These vegetation are of two types. (I) Major vegetation growth of shrubs, bushes, flowering plants and trees. (ii) Minor vegetation, moss and lichen, algae, liverworts and ferns.

STRUCTURAL CONSERVATION:

There are various steps for remedial measures in structural conservation (Dikhit, 2015) of various monuments according to requirement of different sites in different situations. These steps include the removal of major and minor vegetations, checking of the foundation of structures, grouting, drainage system including weep hole etc. restoration of super structures, resetting of old stones, renovating of missing and worn-out stones, replacing old rusted iron dowels, crack filling, pointing, underpinning, rough packing, water tightening, filleting, guniting, curing and porous roofing of ancient structures etc. Conservation actions are different in the rock-cut exposed structures, like rock bolting, rock drain, rock facing etc.

CHEMICAL PRESERVATION:

Followed by structural stability of excavated remains chemical conservation is most essential to reduce the rate and incidence of decay. In order to reduce the severity of changes due to disintegration and disfigurement of monuments and structures chemical treatment is very essential. There are also various stages viz. In first stage, cleaning of monuments and structures (a) for dust and dirt, (b) for oily matter, paint etc., (c) for lime (d) for moss and lichen etc. In second stage treatment with fungicide, in the third stage for salt extraction from the structures and

in fourth stage for consolidation and in last stage, use of preservative on outer surface time to time (Plenderleith & Werner, 1971).

URBAN MANAGEMENT:

The urban system of management (Dikhit, 2007: 142-144) is a complex collection of diverse resources which are interdependent on each other and need to be looked as a whole. Water supply, sewerage, electricity, traffic and car parking are the integrated elements of urban settlement. The management of historic sites must have a broader perspective in terms of social benefit, status, prestige or cultural value than mere commercial interest.

Heritage conservation in urban area is defined as an area of special architectural, historical and cultural interest. It includes the environment of monuments and sites as a whole. The individual building structure to be erected should be regulated by some principles in respect of the height, colour, design etc. Within this designated area the conservation of cultural heritage becomes an essential component of all developmental schemes affecting the peripheral areas also, so that these areas, while continuing to remain vibrant, maintain their visual qualities and traditional character for promoting a sense of pride among the local residents.

In order to maintain the pristine character of the ancient historical buildings/sites, a few suggestions have been mooted out:-

- a) Introduction of suitable statutory provisions for effective protective cover to buildings of historic and architectural importance on the pattern of the traditional methods.
- b) Some form of tax concessions to be provided to persons donating for repair/maintenance of monuments.
- c) Incorporation of the concept of special conservation area in the statutory plans for urban development and to exercise effective planning and control to preserve the essential character of these areas;

- d) Careful research and analytical studies relating to the historic buildings and their surroundings which deserve protection, in the urban areas.
- e) Co-operation of all the concerned parties interested in conservation including Government Departments, Local Bodies, the Indian Heritage Society, voluntary trusts, individual financial supporters/sponsors, authorities for implementation of rules and regulations.
- f) Survey of monuments and conservation areas by concerned Government Agencies, Local Bodies and professional experts.
- g) Publication of inventory or list of such buildings and areas including scholarly analysis of the same by authorities.
- h) Formulation of suitable legislation for protection of the most important monuments and buildings.
- i) Allocation of funds by the central and local Governments for the purpose of repair and restoration of the buildings and monuments.
- j) Framing of statutory provisions enabling to cover large areas containing the historic buildings and surroundings thereof including contiguous areas of scenic beauty for protection.
- k) Intimate association of conservation with tourism and regional planning.

Under the above mentioned circumstances it is pertinent to draw up a conservation plan on the basis of existing planning and developmental efforts at different levels and availability of funds from different sources. Attitudinal and organizational changes are more important than financial resources in implementing a policy of urban conservation. Conservation programme should be given top priority in national policy making. The interest and awareness of the public for preserving national heritage should be stimulated and sustained by encouraging discussions and debates at the levels of schools, colleges and other academic institutions. A legislative and administrative frame work should be introduced at the State and Local levels in order to provide

the basis for protection of buildings and areas of historic and architectural importance. Efforts should be made for close co-operation and interaction between parties interested in conservation including Central and State Governments, Local Bodies, Voluntary Agencies, Commercial and Industrial groups.

As prescribed by the Central Government urban conservation should be an integral part of the management of developmental projects at the metropolitan or small city level. The legal frame work is available in the regional and urban planning legislations of states like Maharashtra and Madhya Pradesh, where amendments on the lines of the British Town Planning Legislation have been made. The Delhi Urban Art Commission Act should be usefully adopted by Odisha government for ensuring the preservation of aesthetic quality of new constructions and to prevent the demolition, inappropriate alteration of existing buildings. The Municipal Acts could be amended to provide for conservation and aesthetic enhancement in respect of :-

- (a) Monuments or group of building of 100 years old or more:
- (b) Buildings or groups of buildings of architectural or historic value not covered by the existing Central or State Legislations for the protection of monuments; and
- (c) Areas of scientific or environmental or historic value worthy of preservation.

Management also covers the improvement of the environment through action against ugly hoardings and overhead electric and telephone lines in the conservation zones. Their removal should be done with the co-operation of the Municipal Agencies. It would also cover restrictions on traffic and on the parking of vehicles and encroachments on the access roads. The Municipal and District Authorities should utilize their existing statutory powers for controlling the visual squalor around the monument area, overhanging wires, ugly advertisements, badly designed public amenities, bus shelters, un-authorised stalls, eating places, high water tanks, construction of Railway line, National Highway and large and small scale industries.

The Ancient Monuments and Archaeological Sites and Remains Act, 1958 and Rule, 1959 of Archaeological Survey of India and Orissa Ancient Monuments and Preservation Act and Rules,

1956 help in protecting the monuments, excavated sites, unexcavated areas, but some more stringent and cogent actions are warranted in this direction.

For better protection of monuments and sites the Government of India, Department of Culture, A.S.I. vide notification No. S.O. 1764, dated 16th June, 1992 has enforced the following rule -:

“The Central Government gave one month’s notice of its intention to declare areas upto 100 meters from the protected limits and further beyond it up to 200 meters near or adjoining protected monuments to be prohibited and regulated areas respectively for purposes of both mining operation and construction”⁶.

3. The Ancient Monuments and Archaeological Sites and Remains (Amendment and Validation) Act, 2010 was enacted to amend the Ancient Monuments and Archaeological Sites and Remains Act, 1958 and to make provision for validation of certain actions taken by the Central Government under the said Act. The Act has come into force (except sections 3, 5, 7 and 8 to 11) on the 23rd day of January, 2010 i.e. the date on which the Ancient Monuments and Archaeological Sites and Remains (Amendment and Validation) Ordinance, 2010 had been promulgated.

The limits of prohibited area and regulated area around the monuments, archaeological sites and remains declared by the Central Government as protected have been specified in the principal Act as 100 m and 200 m, respectively. The limits so fixed may be further extended on the basis of gradation and classification of the monuments.

In respect of regulated area, the Competent Authority may grant permission for construction, reconstruction, repair and renovation on the basis of recommendation of the National Monument Authority duly taking note of heritage bye-laws, which shall be prepared in respect of each protected monument and protected area.

4. Town planning, country planning organization of Central and State Government should regulate urban development scheme by setting archaeological committee. Its main aim and

objectives is to regulate building activities near centrally protected monuments and sites and accordingly the No Objection Certificate from Archaeological Survey of India should be issued to the concerned parties with utmost caution.

The provisions of protected, prohibited and regulated zones are to be applied to the monuments both in urban and rural areas (fig.1). But in most of the cases, due to shortage of government land around the monuments, the adoption of the said provisions are not possible. In case of any difficulties to any monument in urban areas where there is shortage of land a wide road of 10 to 20m should be provided as a substitute to Archaeological Survey of India provisions, so that the visitors could have a look to the monuments from the road side (fig.2) and that will protect the side from further encroachment as well.

Notes

1. *Svarnadri Mahodya*, Chapter-1 , pp. 28-29.
2. *Ekamra Chandrika*, Chapter -1, pp. 19-20.
3. *Ekamra Purana*, Chapter -24,7 ; also see *Ekamra Chandrika*, Chapter -1, p-21.
4. *Ibid.* , Chapter -54; also see *Siva Purana*, Chapter-30; *Ekamra Chandrika*, Chapter -5-8, pp. 4-132 ; *Svarnadri Mahodya*, Chapter-8-16.
5. *Mandala* is a spiritual and ritual symbol in Hinduism and Buddhism that represents the universe. Graphically, it denotes any plan or chart which symbolically represents the cosmos. The basic form of most *manadals* is a square with four gates containing a circle with a centre point. *Manadals* often exhibit radial balance.
6. *Gazette of India*, part-II, section-3(ii) p. 920.

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